

Organometallic control of Ru decoration on CoNi:

From isolated atoms to nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

Engineering surface architectures in multimetallic nanoparticles is crucial for controlling their properties. This work investigates Ru-decorated CoNi nanoparticles prepared by an organometallic approach, yielding Ru as nanoparticles, subnanometric clusters, or isolated atoms. High-resolution electron microscopy (EM) and X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) unambiguously establish these distinct Ru configurations, while X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) reveals that Ru binding energies are influenced by coordination environment. Hydrogen–deuterium isotopic exchange further shows that subnanometric Ru maximizes activity, providing superior per-site reactivity. Together, these results demonstrate how the organometallic approach enables the controlled decoration of a platinum-group metal (i.e., Ru) on base metal (i.e., CoNi) nanoparticles, establishing direct correlations between surface architecture, electronic signatures, and potential catalytic functions.

Decorating base with platinum-group metals is an attractive approach for nanostructured solid catalysts. Integrating active noble metals like Pt, Pd, or Ru with less expensive, abundant, first-row transition metals (e.g., Fe, Co, Cu, Ni) creates multimetallic nanostructures with enhanced catalytic applications.¹⁻³ It is, however, imperative that the atomic environment of the platinum-group metals be controlled for optimal activity. The range of possible species, i.e., isolated atoms, subnanometric clusters (0.5 to <1 nm), or nanoparticles (NPs; 1 to 100 nm), highlights the importance of synthetic control.^{4, 5} Yet current strategies are often size-specific, optimized for

yielding either single atoms, clusters, or nanoparticles. Selective control across all three states within one methodology is rare.⁶

Regarding isolated precious metal atoms on base metal nanostructures, Sykes coined the term single-atom-alloy (SAA) for Pd atoms isolated on a Cu(111) surface via physical vapor deposition.⁷ Transitioning from model surfaces to NP-based catalysts, they prepared Pd-doped Cu/Al₂O₃ via galvanic replacement.⁸ These systems harnessed Pd's affinity for H₂ dissociation, with Pd-Cu proximity favoring hydrogen spillover. Recently, this strategy expanded via vapour deposition, galvanic replacement, and thermal alloying, producing various SAAs or adatom configurations for thermal and electrocatalysis. Examples include Pd₁Ni,⁹ Pd₁Fe,¹⁰ Ru₁Ni,¹¹ Ru₁Co,¹² Ru₁Cu,¹³ or Rh₁Co.¹⁴ SAAs provide high selectivity, bifunctional mechanisms, and alter the density of states near the Fermi Level, impacting adsorbate interactions.¹⁵

NPs and subnanometric clusters on base metal nanostructures are mainly prepared via galvanic displacement or electrodeposition. For instance, using Na₂PdCl₄, subnanometric Pd clusters or NPs have been created on MOF-derived Cu NPs and Ni nanowires.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Similar Pt and Rh precursors have yielded dispersions on carbon-supported Ni particles and a nanoconical Ni electrode, respectively.^{19, 20} These examples show improved electrocatalytic performance due to surface-oxygen, optimized hydrogen adsorption, enhanced reduction activity, and a larger electrochemically active area.

Lately, the organometallic approach has also gained attention for decorating NPs at the nanoscale. This methodology decomposes metal complexes employing H₂ and long-chain surfactants as stabilizers. By selecting precursor and conditions, one can tune size, shape, surface cleanliness, and thus catalytic properties.²¹ Specifically, Ru has decorated Fe(0) and Fe_{2.2}C NPs via [Ru₃(CO)₁₂] decomposition under H₂ at 150 °C,^{22, 23} and CoNi NPs via [Ru(cod)(cot)] (cod =

cyclooctadiene, cot = cyclooctatriene) and H₂ at room temperature.²⁴ Despite their promise, these organometallic strategies prioritize deposition over adjusting decoration size from sub-nanometer to nanometer, motivating our focus on controlled, uniform surface speciation.

Building on prior work with CoNi NPs decorated with multiple Ru species (single atoms, clusters, small NPs),²⁴ we aimed for more precise control over Ru decoration. This is challenging because Ru's thermodynamic tendency to aggregate on the surface or segregate onto bulk Ni or Co.^{11, 25, 26} To address this, we developed a robust methodology using the organometallic approach. We show that changing synthetic parameters, like the Ru precursor or heating method, creates distinct Ru environments, including isolated atoms, clusters, and small NPs, correlating them with hydrogen activation. Such control over decorating metal size has few precedents,⁶ making our approach a valuable tool for functionalizing base with precious metals.

Engineering Ru surface structures

The base support of CoNi nanoparticles was prepared via the hydrogenation of {Co[N(SiMe₃)₂]₂(thf)} and {Ni[ⁱPrNC(CH₃)NⁱPr]₂}, in the presence of palmitic acid (PA), in mesitylene at 120 °C (Section S1.2).^{24, 27} This reproducibly yielded oval-shaped magnetic Co₃Ni₇ NPs with an average diameter of ca. 12 nm (Table S1, Figure S1). XRD data matched our previous work (Figure S15). We earlier defined a face-centered cubic (fcc) CoNi alloy core of ~11 nm with a minor amount of Co hcp clusters (≤ 2 nm), based on HR-EM, XAS, and Rietveld refinement.²⁴ Decoration with Ru would involve decomposing organometallic Ru precursors on these CoNi NPs under reductive conditions.

The starting point was our previous attempt to decorate 80 mg of CoNi NPs using small amounts of [Ru(cod)(cot)] (2.3 mM) in THF, PA as a stabilizer and mild conditions (room temperature, 2 H₂ bars above atmospheric pressure). Initial sonication improved static NP dispersion during Ar

evacuation and H₂ charging. Although this method preserved the CoNi structure, it unselectively produced various surface Ru species, from NPs to single atoms.²⁴ Therefore, here, our initial efforts aimed to optimize conditions for uniform subnanometric decoration with the same precursor.

Our attempts to selectively produce subnanometric Ru species with [Ru(cod)(cot)] failed despite varying temperature, and ligand concentrations. The precursor's limitations are illustrated with a boundary condition in Section S1.3.5. In this synthesis, [Ru(cod)(cot)] was decomposed in THF at 15 °C under ca. 1 Ar + 2 H₂ bars and vigorous stirring, using one-third of the Ru concentration from our previous work (0.75 mM), and a similar protocol. Despite the soft conditions, the synthesis yielded mostly well-formed Ru NPs (1.6 ± 0.9 nm, Table 1, Entry 1, Table S3) following a log-normal distribution (**Ru_{CoNi}-CC-LT**, CC = [Ru(cod)(cot)]; LT = Low Temperature; Figures S12, S13). Interestingly, log-normal profiles can result from parallel random growth events, such as nucleation at various sites or autocatalytic hydrogenation.^{28, 29} This experiment confirms that [Ru(cod)(cot)] is unsuitable as a precursor for uniform subnanometric Ru, favoring NP formation instead.

Table 1. Systematic nomenclature and properties of the synthesized decorated nanoparticles.

Entry	Nomenclature	Precursor	Heating condition/ Decomposition Temperature	Ru NP size (nm)	Ru incorporation (%)
1	Ru _{CoNi} -CC-LT	[Ru(cod)(cot)]	Low Temperature/15 °C	1.6 ± 0.9	51
2	Ru _{CoNi} -CC-TH	[Ru(cod)(cot)]	Thermal Heating/80 °C	1.8 ± 0.9	79
3	Ru _{CoNi} -CC-IH	[Ru(cod)(cot)]	Induction Heating/80-90 °C	1.0 ± 0.5	62
4	Ru _{CoNi} -CO-TH	[Ru ₃ (CO) ₁₂]	Thermal Heating/150 °C	<0.5	100
5	Ru _{CoNi} -CO-IH	[Ru ₃ (CO) ₁₂]	Induction Heating/120 °C	<0.5	94

CC = [Ru(cod)(cot)], CO = [Ru₃(CO)₁₂], LT = low temperature, TH = Thermal (Conventional) Heating, IH = Induction Heating

Accordingly, [Ru(cod)(cot)] was employed to deliberately and selectively generate nanoparticle decorations on CoNi NPs. In this sense, a so-called **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH** (TH= Thermal Heating) sample was prepared by heating the CoNi suspension in THF with [Ru(cod)(cot)] (0.75 mM) and PA at 80 °C under H₂ for 2 h (Table 1, Entry 2, Section S1.3.1). The decoration mainly featured Ru NPs with a hexagonal close-packed (hcp) structure (Figure 1a-d, Figures S2, S8). The sample contained larger NPs (1.8 ± 0.9 nm, Figure S2) than in **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-LT**, with a size distribution that still fit well to a log-normal distribution.

The X-ray absorption near-edge structure (XANES) (Figure S16) and the Fourier transform (FT) of the k²-weighted extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) (Figure S17) were collected at the Ru K-edge. The XANES spectrum of the **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH** sample exhibits features and a white-line energy comparable to the metallic Ru foil reference, indicating a metallic character. The EXAFS R-space plot shows a dominant signal at 2.39 Å, akin to the ruthenium metal, indicating a strong Ru-Ru contribution. Fitting (Figure 1e) confirmed a dominant Ru–Ru path (coordination number 5.7 ± 0.4) between 2.67 and 2.69 Å, similar to the metallic ruthenium foil reference. A minor, shorter Ru–O path was also observed (coordination number 2.1 ± 0.5). This is consistent

with Ru NPs, with the Ru–O arising either from PA ligands or some adventitious oxidation (Figure S19).

The synthesis reproducibility was demonstrated (Figure S2), confirming [Ru(cod)(cot)] as a suitable precursor for the selective decoration of CoNi NPs with small Ru nanoparticles (1–2.5 nm) under mild conditions. Remarkably, synthesis at 80 °C promoted the exclusive formation of Ru NPs while suppressing residual subnanometric species. It also yielded higher Ru incorporation (ca. 79%, Table 1, Entry 2) compared to **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-LT** (ca. 51%, Table 1, Entry 1).

Figure 1. Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH sample. (a) TEM image, (b) HR-TEM image, (c) BF-STEM image, (d) HAADF-STEM image, (e) best fitting of the EXAFS Fourier transformed k^2 -weighted moduli, and (f) plausible structural model in agreement with HR-EM and XAS characterization. Green: hcp Ru; Purple: CoNi fcc (100) example lattice.

To overcome the limitations of conventional heating in dispersing Ru into more subnanometric species at high yield, we switched to induction heating (IH). This technology provides localized and selective heating on the magnetic susceptor's surface,³⁰ accounting for high energy efficiency and rapid heating/cooling.^{31, 32} We recently validated this strategy to improve deposition yields and shell formation on magnetic NPs.³³ In our system, the CoNi NPs themselves can act as susceptors ($M_S = 91 \text{ A}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; $M_R = 3 \text{ A}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$; $H_C = 4 \text{ mT}$; SAR at 93 kHz, 49 mT = $310 \text{ W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)²⁴ for magnetic hyperthermia applications. Therefore, in synthesizing this new sample, i.e. **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH** (IH = Induction Heating; Table 1, Entry 3, Section S1.3.2), the same mixture ([Ru(cod)(cot)], PA, CoNi NPs and THF) was used under conditions analogous to those employed for **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH**. However, heating occurred via magnetic induction (300 kHz, 10 mT), keeping the bulk solution at 80–90 °C (by an IR camera) by localized heating at the magnetic CoNi NPs.

The resulting **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH** (Figure 2) features significantly smaller Ru domains ($1.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ nm}$, Figure S3) than **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH** ($1.8 \pm 0.9 \text{ nm}$, Figure S2). Interestingly, this sample marks a transition from a purely nanoparticle regime (**Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH**) to a more balanced mixture of subnanometric clusters and NPs. Moreover, compared to **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-LT** ($1.6 \pm 0.9 \text{ nm}$), which also contained subnanometric clusters, the distribution is more evenly split, and the Ru incorporation yield increases from 51 to 62% (Table 1, entries 1 and 3; Tables S2 and S3). Though still skewed, the particle size distribution shifts closer to a Gaussian profile than the log-normal character observed under thermal heating. This transition under IH suggests a greater contribution from a burst-type nucleation regime, followed by more synchronous growth.^{34, 35} This behavior likely reflects [Ru(cod)(cot)] decomposition confined at the CoNi surface, favored by the surface-localized heating intrinsic to IH. Consistent with this, TEM images (Figure 2a, Figure S3) show

Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH with Ru more intimately interfaced with the CoNi surface than the more loosely attached species in **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH**.

In this same line, although the XANES profile (Figure S16) closely matches that of the Ru(0) reference, and the FT of the k^2 -weighted EXAFS oscillations is centered at around 2.39 Å, the EXAFS fitting in Figure 2e revealed, not only Ru–Ru coordination (5.5 ± 0.5), but also a clear Ru–Co/Ni interaction (1.7 ± 0.4) (Figure S20). This suggests small Ru clusters strongly interfaced with the bimetallic substrate, supporting TEM observation of smaller Ru sizes.

The good reproducibility results (Figure S3) underscore the value of IH as a surface-selective thermal activation strategy, enabling decoration with smaller NPs and subnanometric clusters, narrow dispersion, and moderate deposition efficiency.

Figure 2. Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH sample. (a) TEM image, (b) HR-TEM image, (c) BF-STEM image, (d) HAADF-STEM image, (e) best fitting of the EXAFS Fourier transformed k^2 -weighted moduli,

and (f) plausible structural model in agreement with HR-EM and XAS characterization. Green: hcp Ru; Purple: CoNi fcc (100) example lattice.

To generate exclusively subnanometric Ru species, we explored the use of the carbonyl complex $[\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ under mild conditions. This precursor is known for its higher tendency to generate isolated Ru species.³⁶⁻³⁸ Due to the higher thermal stability of the precursor, in synthesizing the so-called **Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH** sample, CoNi NPs were suspended in dioxane, treated with $[\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}]$ ($[\text{Ru}] = 0.75 \text{ mM}$) and PA, followed by H₂ addition (2 bar) over Ar (1 bar), and heated to 150 °C for 2 h (Table 1, Entry 4, Section S1.3.3).

This **Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH** material displayed a distinct Ru surface speciation compared to Ru_{CoNi}-CC samples. The deposited Ru structures could not be observed by EM, but only the CoNi NPs (Figure 3a–d, Figure S4). Therefore, these Ru structures are smaller and more dispersed than in **RuCoNi-CC-TH** and **-IH**. ICP-OES confirmed the Ru added was fully incorporated (Table 1, entry 4). Unfortunately, on a high-magnification microscope, STEM-EDX mapping was inconclusive due to beam-induced surface damage across some of these materials (Figure S10). Nonetheless, local EDX and HAADF-STEM suggested the presence of highly dispersed Ru. Bright, highly localized features in the outer NP region (Figure S9) are compatible with atomically dispersed Ru species or small subnanometric clusters.

Further insight into the Ru environment came from XAS. While the XANES spectrum at the Ru K-edge remained characteristic of metallic Ru(0) (Figure S16), the Fourier transform (FT) of the k²-weighted EXAFS oscillations differed from **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH** and **-IH** (Figure S17). The FT modulus displayed a prominent peak at $\sim 2.15 \text{ \AA}$, substantially shifted from the Ru–Ru reference at $\sim 2.39 \text{ \AA}$. This shift suggests a dominant Ru–Co/Ni coordination environment, as expected for partial substitution or intimate contact of Ru with the CoNi lattice. In this line, EXAFS fitting

revealed a significantly reduced Ru–Ru coordination (2.1 ± 0.3), alongside strong Ru–Co/Ni contributions (4.4 ± 0.2), and an additional short-range Ru–C path (1.8 ± 0.3) (Figure S21). These data support the existence of small Ru clusters and even single atoms near the CoNi surface. The short Ru–C path may originate from remnant CO and/or carbide-like Ru–C motifs. Carbides are more typically reported under CO-rich or inert conditions. However, due to the precursor's nature and the presence of small Ru ensembles, the formation of highly localized Ru–C species with interstitial carbon between adjacent Ru atoms, cannot be excluded.³⁹⁻⁴¹

Overall, the **Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH** sample has a different surface architecture than Ru_{CoNi}-CC samples, prepared from [Ru(cod)(cot)]. The [Ru₃(CO)₁₂] pathway uniquely favors subnanometric Ru undetectable by HR-TEM (i.e., <0.5 nm). Attempts to adapt this synthesis to induction heating (IH) conditions, as done for the Ru_{CoNi}-CC series, did not improve Ru dispersion or its incorporation yield (Table 1, Entry 5, Section S1.3.4, Figure S11, Table S3).

Figure 3. Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH sample. (a) TEM image, (b) HR-TEM image, (c) BF-STEM image, (d) HAADF-STEM image, (e) best fitting of the EXAFS Fourier transformed k^2 -weighted moduli, and (f) plausible structural model in agreement with HR-EM and XAS characterization. Green: hcp Ru; Purple: CoNi fcc (100) example lattice.

Electronic signatures of decorating Ru

Since the electronic state of metal sites depends on their local environment,⁴² X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to investigate the Ru in samples with distinct surface architectures. XPS, a surface-sensitive technique with effective electron attenuation lengths of 2-3 nm, gave Ru at.% values in Ru_{CoNi} samples significantly higher than bulk-sensitive methods (ICP-OES, EDX; Table S8). This demonstrates that Ru primarily resides at or near NP surfaces. The fitting procedure was established using reference materials, and full details of the peak fitting strategy and binding energy (BE) determination are provided in Section S1.5.12. However, the Ru(3p_{3/2}) region showed poor signal-to-noise, Ru(3d) analyses being more reliable, as confirmed by Monte Carlo analyses.

The Ru(3d_{5/2}) and Ru(3p_{3/2}) BE showed meaningful variation across the series, from 281.4 and 461.7 eV in Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH to 279.9 and 461.3 eV in Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH (Figure 4). However, the interpretation of BE shifts requires caution, as they reflect a convolution of initial-state (e.g. charge transfer) and final-state effects (e.g. core-hole screening).⁴³ In these samples, the direction of the electron transfer is difficult to predict based only on simple electronegativity considerations, since contradictory BE shifts have been reported.^{11, 44-46} Probably, the observed BE shifts depend strongly on the overall Ru structural environment. In Ru_{CoNi}-CC samples, where Ru forms larger clusters or NPs, positive BE shifts occur in the Ru(3d_{5/2}) component versus a monometallic Ru(0) reference on graphene (280.5 eV) with similar Ru size (Ru_{rGO}-CC; S1.4.2, Tables S6 and S7). This

may result from a not very effective final-state screening and a charge transfer occurring from Ru to Co/Ni. While partial surface oxidation of Ru may contribute to the increase in BE, this scenario is unlikely given the air-free synthesis and handling.

Figure 4. (a) C(1s)/Ru(3d) XP regions, and (b) Ru(3p) regions in the Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH, Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH, and Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH samples. Note: The C components in Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH and Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH are shifted by -0.5 eV and +0.3 eV, respectively, due to using the Fermi Edge as the BE reference, ensuring proper Ru component assignment.

In contrast, **Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH** with subnanometric Ru clusters (<0.5 nm) and single atoms shows a strong negative BE shift across Ru core-levels (ca. 0.5 and 0.4 eV in Ru(3d_{5/2}) and Ru(3p_{3/2}), respectively; Figure 4). Such a shift is somewhat unexpected, as BE upshifts are typically observed with decreasing cluster size, often attributed to initial-state effects, including reduced electron density, a more positive electrostatic potential, and lattice strain.⁴³ However, these initial-state

effects usually dominate size-dependent BE shifts in systems with metal clusters on electronically inert substrates. In our case, the metallic CoNi support is likely to promote charge delocalization at the interface. This delocalization may contribute to enhanced core-hole screening.⁴³ Additionally, higher Ru dispersion in this sample implies a larger interfacial contact with CoNi, potentially facilitating more efficient electronegativity-driven electron transfer to Ru. This effect could result in a more electron-rich Ru species in this system. Still, given the simultaneous influence of initial- and final-state contributions, this interpretation should be approached cautiously. Alternatively, the observed Ru 3d_{5/2} BE may also stem from Ru–C (carbide-like) environments,⁴⁷ which would be consistent with the short Ru–C pathway in our EXAFS fitting. A small residual at ~282 eV (Figure 4a, Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH), typically linked to metal–carbon species,⁴⁸ was noted but excluded from the fit due to its weakness and potential CO residues.

Overall, XPS results indicate Ru BEs on CoNi are strongly affected by surface structure. Larger Ru domains (~1 nm) have positive shifts, while smaller Ru (<0.5 nm) have negative shifts, likely due to enhanced screening and electron donation from Co/Ni.

H/D Exchange reactivity

Ru-decorated CoNi NPs with different surface architectures were evaluated for their ability to activate molecular hydrogen via H/D isotopic exchange. These tests are particularly interesting due to two main reasons. First, combining Ru with a late transition metal surface (Co, Ni) is expected to facilitate H₂ activation.¹¹ Second, tuning Ru dispersion enables the correlation of site structure with hydrogen reactivity, which is crucial for catalytic hydrogenations.

Figure 5. Temperature-dependent results of the H/D isotopic exchange experiments with and Ru_{CoNi}-based materials normalized per a) total Ru, b) amount of exposed Ru according to geometrical estimations.

To assess site-specific activity, the HD/H₂ ratios were normalized in two ways: first, per total Ru atoms in each sample (ICP, Figure 5a), and second, per geometric surface exposure of Ru estimated from size-shape models (TEM and XAS, Figure 5b). Details of these calculations are in Section S1.6. When normalized per total Ru (Figure 5a), **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH** (clusters) shows the highest activity, followed by **Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH** (isolated atoms) and then **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH** (nanoparticles) at a greater distance. This confirms that dispersion enhances Ru utilization in H/D exchange. After geometric surface normalization (Figure 5b), **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-TH** moves closer to the cluster-rich material, reflecting the lower surface fraction of Ru in NPs versus clusters. Nevertheless, **Ru_{CoNi}-CC-IH** remains the most active on a per-site basis. Conversely, the highly isolated Ru species in **Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH** show a drop in apparent per-site activity. We attribute this behavior to partial embedding and residual CO and/or carbide-like species, which reduce the fraction of truly accessible, clean sites. Notably, **Ru_{CoNi}-CO-TH** displays a markedly lower

XPS/ICP Ru at.% ratio (~3) than CC-IH (~9) and CC-TH (~6) (Table S8), consistent with subsurface Ru reducing the truly accessible Ru fraction.

In summary, dispersion improves Ru utilization. Regarding intrinsic reactivity, dispersion enhances per-site activity up to the sub-nanometric cluster regime. In the highly isolated regime (<0.5 nm), embedding and surface residues confound intrinsic reactivity, so we cannot determine whether a lower-size threshold exists at which this trend plateaus or reverses.

To conclude, we present the organometallic approach as a versatile method to decorate CoNi-NPs with Ru under mild conditions, achieving surface architectures from ~2 nm NPs to subnanometric species. The Ru precursor and heating mode influence dispersion, surface access, and cleanliness. [Ru(cod)(cot)] yields cleaner nanoparticles with stronger interfacing in IH synthesis. Conversely, [Ru₃(CO)₁₂] produces highly isolated species (<0.5 nm) with limited access due to partial embedding. XPS shows dispersion-dependent electronic signatures, with more dispersed species having lower BEs. H/D exchange indicates dispersion enhances atom efficiency and H₂ activity per site, offering a new strategy to control catalysis via precious metal decoration.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at:

Detailed experimental methods, ICP-OES and EDX elemental analysis, extra TEM and HR-EM characterization, XRD of the main Ru_{CoNi} materials, extra XAS and EXAFS fitting details, XPS

fitting procedure, raw H/D experiments and explanation of the Ru normalization procedure are included (PDF).

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Notes

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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